

Policy brief

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Recovering diversity in salmon populations and cultures of fishing in the subarctic River Teno – stakeholder meeting and kick-off

The RecoSal project

The RecoSal project aims to support collaborative governance for the recovery of a diverse Atlantic salmon population complex in the large River Teno catchment (in Finnish, Tana in Norwegian, and Deatnu in Sámi) in the northernmost Fennoscandia. Through the establishment of collaborations aiming towards a Living Lab (see Living Lab approach, page 3), the project will connect knowledge production with salmon management, with a special emphasis on the development of population-specific, target-based assessments of genetically diverse salmon populations in a multicultural setting that values Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK) and rights. RecoSal will provide transdisciplinary advice for designing and implementing effective and socially robust governance and management practices with the aim of ecological conservation and recovery of depleted biodiversity.

“I am really impressed and satisfied that such a project is being launched. /.../ Among salmon fishermen, when they meet each other fishing, everyone is equal. We can learn something from this starting point, but the salmon fisherman must also appreciate the researcher's basic background and skills, just as the researcher must respect those he meets on the river. When we recognize each other's value, we can learn something.”

(Representative from Tana municipality)

Locals fishing wild Atlantic salmon from a boat. Photo: Ari Savikko

Map illustrating the study area. The Teno River catchment basin is located between Finland and Norway. Source: Hiedanpää, et al. (2020)

Background – the fishing ban of wild Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*)

The negotiations between Finland and Norway on salmon fishing during the 2021 fishing season resulted in a highly exceptional ban on salmon fishing in the whole Teno River. This was suggested to be a temporary ban that would apply to both rod fishing and fixed gear intended to catch salmon, i.e. weirs, gill nets and drift nets. The restrictions would apply to the Teno River main stem and its tributaries, and to the Tanafjord and an extensive coastal area outside it the size of four municipalities. This connected area would cover the whole life cycle of the Tana salmon population, which is composed of 30 different populations.

The reason for this exceptional restriction was the rapid decline in the Tana salmon stock status detected in the monitoring. According to the Finnish Minister of Agriculture and Forestry, Jari Leppä, the recovery of the salmon stocks had not proceeded as was expected under the (then) present fishing regulations. A total ban was deemed necessary because even restricted fishing would have too much impact on the stocks and slowed down their recovery significantly.

The ban affected the local economy as salmon fishing is one of the most important attractions for tourists, but more importantly also the traditional livelihoods in the area; salmon fishing is a very important aspect of the local Sámi culture and traditional livelihood. The Sámi people around the Teno have been fishing salmon using traditional fishing methods for as long as anyone can remember – and in 2021, for the first time ever, they were not able to practice their traditions.

In 2024, three years later, the ban is still in force and no salmon fishing is possible in the Teno River.

A wild Atlantic salmon. Photo: Jaakko Erkinaro

Traditional fishing gear for wild Atlantic salmon. Photo: Panu Orell

Theoretical framework: Integrative Framework for Collaborative Governance

The Integrative Framework for Collaborative Governance (IFCG) is applied to study and implement collaborative processes in the RecoSal project. The components of the framework are summarized in bullet points below. For more detailed information, see Emerson & Nabatchi (2015).

- System Context consists of different political, legal, socioeconomic, demographic, and environmental conditions.
- Four Drivers emerge that we explore and clarify: Uncertainty, Interdependence, Consequential initiatives and Initiating leadership.
- The System Context and the Drivers provide the impetus for the establishment and formation of what is referred to as Collaborative Governance Regimes, here the potential establishment of Deatnu River Living Lab.
- We apply the concept of Collaboration Dynamics, which consists of three interacting and process-related elements: Principled engagement, Shared motivation and the Capacity for joint action.
- The final variable Generation of Change can be characterized as the production side of collaborative work.

Living Lab approach – Deatnu River Living Lab as an area for collaboration across policy, research and civil society

The Living Lab is envisioned as an outcome after the project end as an arena for collaboration on the future wellbeing of the Teno River among decision-makers (i.e., municipality actors, Sami Parliaments, Tana watercourse fisheries management board (TF), Finnish fishing organizations), researchers from different scientific fields, and civil society such as fishers and knowledge holders. The central actors, their roles and responsibilities in future collaboration will be discussed during the course of four workshops. Our approach was to do smaller meetings in each of the three communities before gathering for larger meetings and Workshops with language interpretation to Finnish, Norwegian and Sámi.

A smaller meeting to introduce the Living Lab concept for local inhabitants and stakeholders in Norway was held in conjunction with a Salmon Dialogue organized by the Nansen Peace Centre and Joddu Wild Salmon Centre. It was held in Tana bru on the 30th of March 2023. The approach to the Living Lab was presented and discussed by those present at the meeting (see Bjärstig & Brattland 2023).

Illustration of the Living Lab approach from the RecoSal project application.
Design: Niina Malinen

Objectives of the first workshop

A series of four co-design workshops will be held during the RecoSal project's implementation, where stakeholders will be informed and engaged, and where the project process will be decided upon in a participatory manner, and visions and outcomes discussed. The aim is the establishment of a permanent and long-term collaboration among actors after the project ends (i.e., a Living Lab).

The first workshop was held in Utsjoki, Finland, in March 2023. In total, 44 people (2 translation technicians, 9 researchers, 33 stakeholders and municipal representatives) from both Finland and Norway participated physically at the meeting, and around 25 participants followed the meeting online.

Right from the start, the research team behind the RecoSal project wanted to hold a large meeting to inform about the project, as well as organize an opportunity to hear local stakeholders' opinions and get feedback on the project. One of the central issues was the establishment of what was presented as a reference group with an advisory role for the project consisting of central actors, rights- and stakeholders in the region.

The first part of the workshop contained presentations of the researchers, the RecoSal project and its different components, i.e. its three work packages (WPs, see page 5). This was done to inform and describe the potential of the project as well as its delimitations to the participants, and give them the opportunity to reflect, ask questions and later also take a stand if they would like to participate or not in the collaborative process.

The second and main part of the workshop was dedicated to participatory planning of the project's implementation based on discussions among all rights- and stakeholders. The researchers emphasized that the RecoSal project builds on a bottom-up approach where the involvement and engagement of locals is key to be able to integrate ILK into the scientific parts of the project and truly talk about co-production of results. All participants were given the opportunity to reflect on three overarching questions related to the project and their own role:

- What to aim for?
- For whom, why, when?
- Responsibilities and expectations?

Overall, the participants were positive and welcomed the RecoSal project with hopes that it in the end will fuel collaboration among different actors in both Finland and Norway, and generate useful results for the area, the salmon, and, not least the management of wild Atlantic salmon.

"We all want to do everything we can to make salmon stocks stronger, and I see that this project is one effort, and also to bring people together in this matter "

(Representative from Saami Council)

Top photo Project presentation in Utsjoki by Juha Hiedanpää. Photo: Niina Malinen

Bottom photo: Open discussion in Utsjoki moderated by Juha Hiedanpää. Photo: Mikko Jokinen

"...it's good to hear that there is prospect for cooperation and dialogue and that's what we've seen as lacking, we hope it will improve, not only on the Norwegian side but also on the Finnish side, our experience is that the connection has been bad, as we experienced last summer"

(Representative from Karasjok rod fishers' organization)

However, several of the participants voiced feelings of being sidestepped by the politicians at the national levels (both Finnish and Norwegian) when the fishing ban was introduced in 2021. Also, there were some skepticisms towards researchers not acknowledging ILK in their research, due to earlier experiences in other research projects. One participant was particular skeptical in that respect, illustrating the importance of high levels of trust between involved actors in this type of collaborative research effort.

"...here we heard that researchers want to hear and learn about the knowledge and skills that local people have. This is the first time I've heard of this regarding Teno's research. We have experienced that our knowledge or expertise has been mocked or ignored. E.g. issues related to salmon prey. This is related to the trust that we are starting, where the same researchers who have previously looked over the affairs of the local people, it is part of ruining the trust"

(Representative from Tana watercourse fisheries management board (TF))

The Sami Parliament of Finland, referring to their new guidelines for research in the field of Sámi cultural heritage and traditional knowledge, emphasized that the Sámi people must be able to participate at different stages, including in planning, reviewing studies and evaluating the results, so that there are no results they do not know about and no conflict about the ownership of the knowledge and results, and that they must be included and part of the project not only in the beginning and end, but throughout the whole process.

At the end of the workshop, the participants and research team discussed what is possible to achieve and realistic within the scope of the RecoSal project, where several participants highlighted the importance of also detecting and including what happens to wild Atlantic salmon at sea and how it impacts the populations. This is, however, a shortcoming of the RecoSal project as it is delimited solely to the Teno River. By settling these expectations, the involved actors became more aligned.

Overview of work packages (WP) 1-3 in the RecoSal project

WP1: Bayesian population modelling for assessing the status of Teno Atlantic salmon populations.

Objectives: 1) to provide probability-based evaluation of the status of Teno salmon populations that incorporates the life cycle dynamics of various sub-populations, enables estimation of natural and fishing mortalities both at sea and in rivers, as well as estimation of stock specific targets and spawner stocks; 2) to investigate by simulation models how incorporation of ILK and predation effects could help improve the model structure and overall assessment methods including setting reference points; 3) to draft a long-term plan for designing the structure of a comprehensive model framework, enabling incorporation of all relevant information and provision of essential advice for decision making.

WP2: Exploring collaborative governance modes and outcomes for the Teno River.

Objectives: 1) to produce a first-generation participatory planning model for collaborative salmon management in the Teno region and provide advice on its applicability to the existing and emerging collaborations in governance; 2) to investigate through Integrative Framework for Collaborative Governance (IFCG) i) how the existing and potential new collaborations in the Teno region support cohesion, harness development potentials, cope with trade-offs, and provide legitimate routes towards the planning of sustainable salmon management, and ii) the capacity to establish long-term collaborative processes to ensure sustainable and socially acceptable salmon management in the Teno region.

WP3: Towards a resilient future for salmon: Integrating biological and governance models in a common transdisciplinary framework.

Objective: to synthesise findings of WP1 and WP2, and ensure that all co-produced knowledge meet the formal decision requirements (rules and protocols) on Teno salmon management in a useful, understandable form for decision-makers, stakeholders, and Indigenous and local communities, i.e., the Living Lab participants, to be motivated and capable of applying integrated knowledge in the recovery plan process.

Boats used for wild Atlantic salmon fishing in the Teno River. Photo: Ari Savikko

Next step and recommendations

Based on this first workshop, some practicalities and challenges for the continued collaborative work in the RecoSal project (and other project working in the area involving local stakeholders and indigenous rights holders) were identified:

- The choice between the roles of actors as participants in the steering of the project, and being part of a reference group of knowledge holders useful to research, must be sorted out and decided upon. The Saami Council expressed that Sámi should be part of the steering of the project and not only in advisory capacity.
- There must be technical solutions and preparedness for translation between several languages (Finnish, Norwegian and Sami) at physical meetings, but also in the texts and materials produced.
- Different working methods should be considered: it is not optimal to send ten-page reports to fishermen and ask for comments: oral discussions are often preferred.
- Researchers should not expect people to join projects for free. If the researchers are at work, the participants should also be compensated for the time spent, and accordingly some compensation should be included in applications that involve a high degree of collaboration in the project.
- When working with ILK, there should be some form of local steering group that can protect and formalize the use of ILK in the co-production of knowledge/results, as knowledge holders may not want their knowledge to be openly distributed to the public.
- Free, prior, and informed consent (FPIC) for all involved actors on individual basis is an obvious part of sound research, but the ethical approval of projects involving indigenous peoples and ILK should also be handled on a community basis and this must find more elaborated and formalized ways to be conducted in the future by the Sami parliaments in Finland and Norway to reduce the burden for both indigenous participants and researchers.

As a conclusion, it became evident that actors needed more information on what to expect from collaboration and involvement in the project, and the project needed more information on what relevant topics the local population desired to investigate as part of the project. The next workshop was planned for Karasjok, Norway, in the fall 2023 as a scoping workshop on the possibilities and challenges to conduct collaborative salmon research, and what themes to focus on for the research collaboration.

Further reading and references:

Bjärstig, T., & Brattland, C. (2023). Presentation "Introduksjon til prosjektet RecoSal og LivingLab" and meeting notes from meeting in Tana bru. RecoSal project.

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Project partners

Jaakko Erkinaro (project coordinator), Juha Hiedanpää, Mikko Jokinen, Henni Pulkinen, Niina Malinen, Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho, Taru Rikkinen and Antti Rätty from the Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke); Camilla Brattland and Torstein Pedersen from UiT - the Arctic University of Norway; Martin Svenning and Morten Falkegård from the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA); and Therese Bjärstig from Umeå University, Sweden.

Authors

Therese Bjärstig and Camilla Brattland

Publisher

Malin Eklund Wimelius

Contact

Department of Political Science, Umeå University

Department of Political Science

Umeå University

www.umu.se/department-of-political-science/

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